

Studies in the Cyclo-octane Series: Part III. Condensation of Cyclo-octanone with Arylamines and Preparation of Some Derivatives of 1-Arylamino-cyclo-octane

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Condensation of cyclo-octanone with a number of arylamines and aqueous potassium cyanide in presence of acetic acid has been described. These cyanides have been converted into the corresponding amides and acids. On keeping some of the cyanides get isomerised to the corresponding isocyanides which in few cases could be distilled and characterised as their hydrochlorides.

Earlier interest in the chemistry of 1-arylamino-cycloalkanes was confined to the synthesis of indoxyl spirocycloalkanes^{1,2} and failure in the preparation of indoxyl spiro-cyclopentane brought in a new interest regarding the part played by the cyclopentane ring during the cyclisation of 1-anilinocyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid. The corresponding cyclohexane analogue was, however, later obtained by the cyclisation of 1-anilinocyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid³. Later workers⁴ carried out similar series of reactions from the point of getting some information on the boat-chair isomerism of the cyclohexane ring.

These arylamino compounds have, of late, gained further importance and the studies⁵ carried out on the pyrolysis of 1-anilino-cyclopentane, -cyclohexane and cycloheptane-1-nitriles and 1-carboxylic acids revealed that maximum yields of the cycloalkylene nitriles and carboxylic acids were obtained with the cycloheptane derivatives.

More recently, the liquid phase pyrolysis⁶ of 1-anilino-1-cyanocycloalkanes (I; $n=2, 3, 4$) has also been studied in the hope of preparing unsaturated nitriles but the results revealed that pyrolysis leads to primary equilibrium dissociation into the corresponding anil (II; $n=2, 3, 4$) and hydrocyanic acid with no competing primary scission to give the olefinic nitrile and aniline:

Since no work has been done on similar condensation of aromatic bases with cyclo-octanone, it was thought of interest to study the behaviour of the eight membered ring during this set of reactions especially the cyclisation of 1-anilinocyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acid and then to compare it with the lower analogues.

1. S. G. P. Plant and J. F. Facer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 237.
2. F. Tiemann, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2039.
3. R. L. Betts, R. Musprat and S. G. P. Plant, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1310.
4. M. W. Baksh, R. D. Desai, R. F. Hunter and M. Hussain, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1159.
5. W. C. Bain and P. D. Ritchie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 4407.
6. W. C. Bain, P. D. Ritchie and A. E. Wright, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1454.

Thus, cyclo-octanone was condensed with aniline, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, isomeric anisidines, *o*- and *p*-phenetidines, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline and β -naphthylamine in glacial acetic acid and aqueous potassium cyanide to give the corresponding 1-arylamino-cyclo-octane-1-nitriles (III; X=CN). These on controlled hydrolysis with concentrated sulphuric acid at room temperature furnished the amides III; X=CONH₂; subsequent hydrolysis of these with sulphuric acid (40%) or preferably with alcoholic concentrated hydrochloric acid yielded the acids (III; X=COOH).

The hydrolysis of the nitriles to the amides stage proceeded smoothly except in the case of 1-*o*-anisidino-cyclo-octane-1-nitrile where sulphonation had taken place in preference to hydrolysis. Attempts to obtain indoxylspirocyclo octane by the cyclisation of 1-anilino-cyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acid were not successful like the corresponding cyclopentane and cycloheptane⁷ carboxylic acids which failed to cyclise.

Further, 1-arylamino-cyclo-octane-1-nitriles got isomerised to the corresponding isonitriles; such isomerisations have also been observed with cycloheptane nitriles but not with their lower analogues and this difference in behaviour appears to be in some way related to the size of the ring. We are also led to believe that the nature of the substituents in the benzene ring of the aromatic amines plays a part in this isomerisation, as some 1-arylamino-cyclo-octane-1-nitriles isomerised more quickly than others on keeping, though no comparative and quantitative studies have been made in this direction.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Anilinocyclo-octane-1-cyanide: A solution of potassium cyanide (3.25 g; 0.05 mol) in water (6 ml) was added with shaking to a well cooled solution of cyclo-octanone (3.15 g, 0.025 mol) and aniline (2.32 g; 0.025 mol) in glacial acetic acid (12 ml) contained in a glass stoppered conical flask (100 ml) and the reaction mixture kept overnight at room temperature. The solid which separated out was filtered, washed and dried; the crude product melted at 63.5°. On crystallisation from petrol(40-60°) pure 1-*anilinocyclo-octane-1-cyanide* was obtained in colourless needles and had m.p. 68-9° (Yield: 4.8 g; 88.4%). (Found: C, 78.5; H, 8.7. C₁₅H₂₀N₂ requires C, 78.9; H, 8.8%).

1-Anilinocyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acid amide: 1-Anilinocyclo-octane-1-cyanide (4 g) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (20 ml) contained in a conical flask (100 ml) and kept at room temperature for 48 hr. The reaction product was poured over crushed ice (200 g), neutralized with strong ammonium hydroxide solution when a solid was deposited. It was filtered, washed and dried and had m.p. 146-8°; pure 1-*anilinocyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acid amide* was crystallised from dilute ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 151° (Yield: 3.6 g; 83%). (Found: C, 72.9; H, 9.0. C₁₅H₂₂ON₂ requires C, 73.1; H, 9.0%).

7. P. R. Desai, R. D. Desai, G. S. Saharia and B. R. Sharma, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 525.

1-Anilinocyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acid: The above acid amide (3g) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (25 ml) contained in a R. B flask (250 ml); water (30 ml) was cautiously added and the contents heated on a sand bath first at low flame (30 mts) and then strongly under reflux for 6 hr. The reaction product was cooled, neutralized with strong ammonium hydroxide solution and acidified with glacial acetic acid; the deposited solid was filtered, washed, dried and had m p 169-70°. Pure *1-anilino cyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acid* was crystallised from dilute ethanol in colourless needles, m p 173.4°. (Yield: 2.7 g. 75%). (Found: C, 72.6; H, 8.4. $C_{15}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 72.8; H, 8.5%).

Attempted synthesis of indoxylspiro-cyclo-octane: A mixture of *1-anilinocyclo octane-1-carboxylic acid* (4 g) and KOH (10 g) was carefully heated in a nickel crucible to 340-50° and maintained at this temperature for 30 minutes. The reaction mixture was cooled, lixiviated with water in a pestle and mortar and filtered. The residue on drying was distilled under vacuum when no product was obtained.

TABLE I

1-Arylamino-cyclo-octane-1-cyanides.

Name	Solvent	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	%Found		% Requires	
					C	H	C	H
1. 1-Anilino	Petrol	68-9	88.4	$C_{15}H_{20}N_2$	78.5	8.7	78.9	8.8
2. 1- <i>p</i> -Toluidino-	,,	71	83	$C_{16}H_{22}N_2$	78.9	9.2	79.2	9.1
3. 1- <i>m</i> -Toluidino-	Benzene-petrol	81	86	$C_{16}H_{22}N_2$	79.2	8.9	79.2	9.1
4. 1- β -Naphthylamino-	Benzene	106	94	$C_{19}H_{22}N_2$	81.7	8.0	81.9	7.9
5. 1- <i>p</i> -Anisidino-	Petrol	62	90	$C_{16}H_{22}ON_2$	74.1	8.4	74.3	8.5
6. 1- <i>m</i> -Anisidino-	Benzene-petrol	71	80.4	$C_{16}H_{22}ON_2$	74.4	8.7	74.4	8.6
7. 1- <i>o</i> -Anisidino	,,	70	50	$C_{16}H_{22}ON_2$	74.1	8.6	74.4	8.6
8. 1- <i>p</i> -Chloroanilino-	,,	77	81	$C_{15}H_{19}N_2Cl$	68.5	7.3	68.5	7.2
9. 1- <i>p</i> -Bromoanilino-	,,	97	83	$C_{15}H_{19}N_2Br$	58.7	6.2	58.6	6.1
10. 1- <i>p</i> -Phenetidino-	Petrol	64	77.3	$C_{17}H_{24}ON_2$	74.8	8.9	74.9	8.8
11. 1- <i>o</i> -Phenetidino-	Could not be crystallised and used as such for subsequent reactions.							

Petrol 40-60° was used throughout.

TABLE II

1-Arylamino-cyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acid amides.

Name	Solvent	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%Found		% Requires	
					C	H	C	H
1. Anilino-	Ethanol	151	83	$C_{15}H_{22}ON_2$	72.9	9.0	73.1	9.0
2. 1- <i>p</i> -Toluidino-	,,	163	80	$C_{16}H_{24}ON_2$	74.0	9.3	73.8	9.3
3. 1- <i>m</i> -Toluidino-	,,	156	81.7	$C_{16}H_{24}ON_2$	73.7	9.1	73.8	9.3
4. 1- β -Naphthylamino-	,,	179	82	$C_{19}H_{24}ON_2$	76.7	8.1	76.9	8.1
5. 1- <i>p</i> -Anisidino-	,,	139	84	$C_{16}H_{24}O_2N_2$	69.3	8.8	69.5	8.7
6. 1- <i>m</i> -Anisidino-	,,	124	81.5	$C_{16}H_{24}O_2N_2$	69.4	8.8	69.5	8.7
7. 1- <i>o</i> -Anisidino-	,,	147	20	$C_{16}H_{24}O_2N_2$	69.4	8.6	69.5	8.7
8. 1- <i>p</i> -Chloroanilino-	,,	186	71	$C_{15}H_{21}ON_2Cl$	63.9	7.4	64.1	7.4
9. 1- <i>p</i> -Bromoanilino-	,,	182	61.4	$C_{15}H_{21}ON_2Br$	55.2	6.3	55.3	6.4
10. 1- <i>p</i> -Phenetidino-	,,	148	87.5	$C_{17}H_{26}O_2N_2$	70.2	9.1	70.3	9.0
11. 1- <i>o</i> -Phenetidino-	,,	105	76	$C_{17}H_{26}O_2N_2$	70.2	9.2	70.3	9.0

TABLE III

1-Arylamino-cyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acids.

Name	Solvent	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%Found		%Requires	
					C	H	C	H
1. 1-Anilino-	Dil. Ethanol	173-4	75	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	72.6	8.4	72.8	8.5
2. 1- <i>p</i> -Toluidino-	Benzene	154	83.3	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	73.7	8.6	73.5	8.8
3. 1- <i>m</i> -Toluidino-	,,	169-70	83.3	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	73.4	8.7	73.5	8.8
4. 1- β -Naphthylamino-	Dil. Ethanol	169.	40	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	76.5	7.9	76.7	7.8
5. 1- <i>p</i> -Anisidino-	Dil. Ethanol	170	77.5	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₃ N	69.2	8.2	69.2	8.3
6. 1- <i>m</i> -Anisidino-	Benzene	153	80	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₃ N	69.1	8.5	69.2	8.4
7. 1- <i>p</i> -Chloroanilino-	,,	161-2	66.6	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCI	63.9	7.2	63.9	7.1
8. 1- <i>p</i> -Bromoanilino-	Dil. Ethanol	151	60	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ NBr	55.2	6.2	55.2	6.1
9. 1- <i>p</i> -Phenetidino-	Benzene	176-7	85	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ N	70.0	8.4	70.0	8.6
10. 1- <i>o</i> -Phenetidino-	Dil. Ethanol	137	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ N	69.8	8.8	70.0	8.6

Cyclo-octanone (0.025 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid was similarly condensed with *m*- and *p*-toluidines, isomeric anisidines, *o*- and *p*-phenetidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline and β -naphthylamine (each 0.025 mol) in presence of aqueous potassium cyanide (0.05 mol). The products, 1-arylamino-cyclo octane-1-cyanides obtained are listed out in table-I. These nitriles on partial hydrolysis furnished the corresponding amides (Table-II) which on subsequent hydrolysis yielded the acids given in Table-III.

1-*p*-toluidino cyclo-octane-1-isocyanide obtained from the mother liquor of the corresponding cyanide (Compound 2-Table I) distilled at 44-6°/1.5 mm. It was characterised as the *hydrochloride*, m.p. 205°. (Found: C, 69.1; H, 8.1. C₁₆H₂₃N₂ Cl requires C, 69.6; H, 8.2%).

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